

Critical Review of David Carr's "Values, Virtues and Professional Development in Education and Teaching"

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Abstract

This article review examines David Carr's **Values, Virtues and Professional Development in Education and Teaching**, focusing on his argument that teaching is fundamentally a moral profession grounded in virtues rather than a purely technical occupation. The review outlines Carr's rejection of empiricist conceptions of values and his distinction between values as tastes, commitments, and stable dispositions. It also discusses his emphasis on moral and intellectual virtues, particularly practical wisdom (**phronesis**), as essential qualities of effective teachers. The paper critically evaluates Carr's claim that personal and professional morality are closely connected, questioning the practicality of this position and the challenges of distinguishing professional faults from personal flaws, assessing genuine virtue, and integrating virtue-based education into teacher preparation. Drawing on the works of Campbell (2003), Shapira-Lishchinsky (2011), and El Kassimi and Jmila (2025), the review suggests possible ways to address these concerns through ethical reflection, critical-incident analysis, peer observation, student feedback, and reflective practice. It concludes that although Carr's account is primarily philosophical and raises practical questions about the cultivation and evaluation of virtues, it offers a compelling framework for understanding teaching as a profession requiring moral integrity, sound judgment, and intellectual virtue alongside technical competence.

Keywords: Teacher education; Virtue ethics; David Carr; Professional development; Educational philosophy; Teacher professionalism.

Introduction:

In his article “Values, Virtues, and Professional Development in Education and Teaching”, David Carr rejects empiricist views that reduce values to mere tastes. For him, values have an objective, principled basis (reason). He argues that teaching cannot be reduced to technical skills or competences, or what’s called a set of “off-the-peg” skills; if all it takes to be a good teacher is just mastering pedagogical skills, then any rogue or rascal might become a good teacher (Carr,1993; Hyland,1993,1994). This review evaluates Carr’s central claim that virtues are moral, intellectual(*phronesis*), and principled dispositions that cannot be simply turned on or off, and should not be understood as tastes, commitments, or technical skills. Thus, Carr assumes a strong continuity between personal and professional morality. The article presents a strong philosophical analysis that challenges modern skill-based teacher training, and questions practicality (empirical support), and measurement.

Summary:

In David Carr article “Values, Virtues and Professional Development in Education and Teaching”, his main argument is that teaching is a moral profession, not just a technical job. He criticizes the empiricist view that sees values as mere tastes; for example, saying “I like chewing gum” expresses taste, but saying “I value chewing gum” sounds strange. Thus, values require reasons (justifications). Another reason why values as “principled preferences” are not enough is that valuing something doesn't mean we rigidly follow it. For example, someone may value going to the dentist and still avoid it because of fear of pain; this is called “akrasia” (weakness of will). Principled commitments are also not enough for teachers because they can become just rule-following and self-control, which Aristotle referred to as “continence”. The moral motivation of the virtuous differs from that of the continent” self-controlled” because of a stronger unity between the ‘intellectual’ and ‘appetitive’ parts of the soul; the virtuous have ‘educated’ their passions and appetites to a point where they (should) no longer even desire what is not virtuous. Thus, virtues are principled dispositions that are stable and properties of a person's character that cannot be turned on or off whenever the person wants to. As Aristotle (1925) defines, virtues are “dispositions concerned with choice, lying in a mean between extremes.” Furthermore, for many professions like law and medicine, a lack of warmth or empathy might not be counted as a professional fault. Unlike this, nursing, ministry, social work, and teaching require deep personal virtues like empathy and moral integrity because the nature of the work requires these virtues. Thus, teaching is not just a set of “off-the-peg” competences, which are standardized teaching techniques that teachers are expected to use everywhere, as if one method works perfectly for every student and class. On this view, “off-the-peg”, since all it takes to be a good teacher is to have mastered relevant pedagogical or managerial skills, any rogue or rascal might become a good teacher. Instead, he believes that real teaching requires intellectual virtues (*phronesis* or practical wisdom) because classroom decisions are context-dependent and morally loaded. Carr concludes that good teaching requires the cultivation of a whole set of virtues as moral, intellectual, and practical rather than mere mastery of technique. In other words, teachers should not be trained as technicians but as virtuous practitioners whose moral and intellectual character enables genuine authority, sound judgment, and meaningful teaching.

Analysis:

Carr's arguments are well-structured and grounded in a clear distinction between different senses of values, such as principled preferences, commitments, and dispositions. He uses Aristotle's distinction between moral virtues, "continence" self-control, and intellectual virtues (phronesis/practical wisdom), which gives his arguments a clear conceptual framework. He convincingly illustrates that teaching is not merely a technical skill, a set of "off the peg", but a moral profession that requires practical wisdom and sensitivity to context. He strengthens this point by distinguishing between teaching as an activity and teaching as a professional role. A teacher may succeed in the activity sense "I have just been teaching mathematics to 1B", but the professional role cannot be fulfilled without upholding moral aims such as trust and justice. These moral virtues are what allow the teacher to be flexible and responsive, rather than functioning like a machine that teaches without recognizing students' needs or reactions. Students actively absorb knowledge and then reflect it back in forms of reactions, questions, or facial expressions that suggest either understanding or confusion. And this is precisely what a technical teacher cannot achieve. Carr emphasizes that even knowledge and skill depend on intellectual virtues such as honesty, accuracy, diligence, and open-mindedness.

However, several aspects of Carr's argument invite critical questioning. For instance, Carr suggests continuity between personal and professional morality, which might be unrealistic or intrusive. Expecting teachers to possess moral virtues in their personal and professional life might appear demanding or impractical because humans are weak and naturally imperfect. So, he does not fully address whether a teacher with moral flaws might still perform well professionally; what specifically is counted as a "professional fault" and a "private/personal" flaw? Additionally, he argues that good teaching requires moral virtues, He does not specify the extent to which a teacher's personal life should matter. Where should the line be drawn? How can we know whether a teacher is genuinely virtuous? What if he is just performing/pretending to be virtuous? And are virtues even measurable in a meaningful way? Indeed, virtues as Carr (2007) emphasizes cannot be reduced to measurable behaviors (cannot be measured like technical skills) because they involve internal motivations and practical wisdom, not merely outward actions, but there are evaluative tools that can reveal virtues in professional practice. Moreover, Carr relies heavily on philosophical reasoning and provides limited empirical evidence to support claims about virtue-based practice. Furthermore, although he insists that virtues such as courage, justice, and phronesis are essential, he does not explain how teacher education programs can operationalize virtues or integrate them alongside technical competencies.

Insights:

Carr's argument aligns well with contemporary discussions about moral values in education. Teachers influence not only academic learning but also students' ethical awareness, for this reason, the knowledgeable teacher needs intellectual virtues no less than the authoritative teacher needs moral. However, as Carr acknowledges implicitly, teacher education programs tend to prioritize technical skills "off-the-peg" over virtues because virtues are difficult to measure, observe, or standardize. Thus, this raises these key questions: *I agree that virtues are extremely important in teaching but:* •what specifically is counted as a "professional fault" and a "private/personal" flaw?

•How can we determine whether a teacher is genuinely virtuous? Or how can we evaluate/approximate virtues?

•And how can virtues be integrated into teacher-training programs alongside technical competencies?

To address this, **Firstly**, (Campbell, 2003, p. 3) illustrates the distinction between professional faults and personal flaws by emphasizing that teaching is an ethical profession. She asserts that "***Ethical knowledge relies on teachers' understanding and acceptance of the demands of moral agency as professional expectations implicit in all aspects of their day-to-day practice***". This means that when a teacher fails to see or act on the moral/ethical dimension of their everyday professional work (e.g. classroom interactions, decisions about students, fairness, respect) that counts as a professional fault. Nonetheless, "***Ethical teachers need not be perfect. They do need, however, to be receptive to the development and enrichment of their own ethical knowledge***" (Campbell, 2003, p. 140), this is the distinction between professional fault and personal imperfection/flaw. **Secondly**, Ethical dilemma tasks (critical incidents) are one of the best ways to observe practical wisdom and to approximate/evaluate virtues. Shapira-Lishchinsky (2011) conducted a study using critical incidents, where teachers described real classroom ethical dilemmas, to analyze their moral reasoning and professional virtues. Her findings show that teachers' responses reveal underlying values such as fairness, care, integrity, and responsibility, demonstrating that ethical-dilemma tasks can serve as a practical method to approximate virtue in teaching practice (pp. 649–654). Also, Peer Observation, where colleagues can see whether a teacher consistently demonstrates fairness, patience, care, and respect. In addition to that student Feedback surveys also can help in evaluating whether a teacher is just, respectful, and caring. **Finally**, virtues can be integrated into teaching programs through reflection and practice AS El Kassimi, I., & Jmila, M. (2025) explained "**Teacher professional development is essential for any teacher training program. To achieve this, pre-service teachers should engage in various activities and practices. One important practice is reflection, which can help teachers improve both their professional and personal performance**". This suggested method can bridge the gap between Carr's philosophical claims and the practical realities of teacher education, making the cultivation of virtues both observable and professionally relevant.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, Carr's article offers a compelling philosophical argument for understanding teaching as a moral profession grounded in virtues rather than mere technical competence. He successfully distinguished between different senses of values (mere tastes, commitments, and dispositions), and between teaching as an activity and a professional role. Although the article is largely theoretical and raises questions about how virtues can be practically measured or taught, it provides an important reminder that teaching is a moral practice rooted in the teacher's character rather than a merely technical function. Ultimately, Carr's work remains valuable for reminding us that teaching is not simply about transmitting knowledge, but about forming individuals through relationships built on trust, justice, and moral integrity. For Carr, good teachers of moral, epistemic, and craft virtue are those to whom positive moral association, knowledge, and its skillful presentation are as significant for their own personal development as they are for the development of others.

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